

A STUDY ON SOCIAL AND POLITICAL CONFLICTS IN MANOHAR MALGONKAR'S "A BEND IN THE GANGES"

P. Nagarjuna

Research Scholar (Part-Time)

Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur, AP

Lecturer in English, GDC (M) (A), Anantapur

Abstract: *Manohar Malgonkar published "A Bend in the Ganges" when he was fifty-one years old. He captured the revolutionary fervor of a generation as well as the deadly wounds left in the wake of partition. He is a writer of the traditional school of novelists. His writings are mostly historical and political. They show an authentic picture of social reality.*

A Bend in the Ganges is concerned with the theme of an individual's quest for fulfillment in moral identity. The story is fictitious but based on facts such as – Jalianwala Bagh, World War II, and the Japanese advent into Andaman, communal riots, and partition. This novel is concerned with four characters – Gian Talwar, Debidayal, Shafi Usman, and Basu. These characters are drawn from different layers of society.

This study will try to probe the Indo-British relationship portrayed in this work and examine social and political issues. It is also intended to study how Malgonkar has portrayed the changes in interpersonal relationships in different forms under different circumstances. His deep knowledge of human nature can be seen in his portrayal of friendship and enmity changing under the pressure of circumstances.

Keywords: *Partition, Indo-British Relationship, social, political issues, interpersonal relationship.*

INTRODUCTION:

Manohar Malgonkar (1913-2010) occupies an important place in Indian writing in English, particularly for his historical fiction with a political backdrop. He wrote novels that have a blend of history, romance, and military life.

Conflict is a relationship between two or more individuals and groups who have or think that they have incompatible goals and needs. Conflict is neither negative nor positive. It has a positive aspect when it directs attention to the injustices that need to be addressed when it promotes much-needed change in an organization and systems and leads you to creative problem-solving. The negative aspects of conflict or destructive behavior, the pain and the trauma, and the wastage of resources that would have been spent on creative activities. *"But religion that seeks to unite people and provide them with the meaning in life must be promoted to counter the selfish materialistic tendencies of capitalism and consumerism."*¹

Social life is the summary of the interaction among individuals, families, and social groups. A Writer reveals the peculiarities of society in his writings. The characters created by him are seen occupying a particular position in the place and time of action.

Social conflict is evident when one social group compares its gains and feels that it is being marginalized by other groups. It is also said that when it perceives that it is being deprived of what is duly available to other groups in the society. Social conflict revolves around social

power. Every person participating in social interaction tries to maximize his gain at the expense of the other person involved. This situation leads to a struggle to win and keep others away from their goal. Political and social policies may contribute to each of the three stages of conflict: Pre-conflict, conflict, and post-conflict. Political conflict involves the confrontation of powers. Political violence is a production of social conflict.

The Partition of India in 1947 was the change of political borders and the division of other assets that accompanied the dissolution of the British Raj in the Indian subcontinent and the creation of two independent dominions in South Asia: India and Pakistan. Partition of India remains a painful watershed movement in the Indian freedom struggle. The author has maintained a neutral tone throughout the novel and has not made any prejudice while writing it. The author's historical awareness is striking.

This novel is considered the best book of the year 1964 by E.M. Forster. Like Khushwant Singh's "A Train to Pakistan", this work is also close to time and events of the partition. Malgonkar depicted events of partition riots and gained in depth by probing the validity of ideologies of violence and non violence and their relevance to life. The novelist purpose of describing the period seems to be twofold. The first is to introduce to the reader as an objective chronicler, the basic ingredients of the political scene – the struggle for emancipation, the two parallel movements symbolizing two extreme cults – the violent and non violent, the injection of communal virus, the parting of ways, the Muslim outcry for division, the Quit India phase and finally the removal of the shackles, climaxed by the creation of two separate states – India and Pakistan. The second intention of the author is to probe into the ideology of Ahimsa, non-violence and truth, and ultimately affirm the importance of non-violence, truth and love on life.

The novel is divided into thirty-six chapters. These chapters form three informal parts. Chapters one to thirteen cover the period between 1937 and 1939 and are set in West Punjab. Chapters fourteen to twenty-three are set in the Andamans and cover a period of four years from 1939 to 1942. Chapters twenty-four to thirty-six cover the period between 1942 to 1947 which brought the country its independence and the partition.

*Some characters in the novel, like Basu are the author's spokesperson who deride, condemn and ridicule the very concept of non-violence as propounded by Gandhi.*² Malgonkar introduces several characters like Sundari, Gopal, Tekchand, Aji, Hari, Basu, and Patrick Mulligan. All these characters reveal the richness of life from many points of view and provide a viable background for the violent action of the novel. He makes his characters realistic and complex. They can't be drawn into neat categorizations of good and bad.

*"Boycott British goods! Mahatma Gandhi-ki jai! Victory to Mahatma Gandhi"*³ The story begins with the dramatic scene of burning British goods, an introduction to the philosophy of nonviolence, and Gian and Sundari's induction into the ideology. At one level, it is the story of two young men who jump into the freedom struggle - Debi Dayal, the son of an affluent family in Duriabad, and Gian Talwar from a poor family in a village. Graduates of the same college are motivated to join the freedom struggle but they choose different paths.

*"Indo-British relationship portrayed in A Bend in the Ganges is purely political. There are three facets of this relationship portrayed in the novel – the attitude of the ordinary Indian, of the educated and enlightened, and of the Indian capitalist class."*⁴ The first scene opens in a public square where Gandhi is sitting on a dais, quietly spinning cotton on a spool, and his associates explain the purpose of boycotting foreign goods. Gian is studying in Duriabad, a town in North-West of Punjab in a college where he meets Debidayal, the son of Dewan Bahadur Tekchand Kerwad, of Kerwad Construction Company. Debidayal is a revolutionary and member of a party called "The Freedom Fighters". Shafi Usman is their leader and together, these young patriots engage in various terrorist activities like blowing

bridges, removing fish plates from railway tracks, and such other acts. However, they land in trouble when they smuggle explosives from Tekchand's factory and blow up an Air Force plane.

Gian and Debidayal are the victim of circumstances and of their upbringing. Gian's and Debi's backgrounds are widely different as also their immediate motivations. Debi was a young boy of thirteen, he had seen his mother being almost molested by a Scottish soldier, while he himself paralyzed with anger and shame, could not do anything. This feeling forced him to become a member of the band of freedom fighters who were fervent patriots. Their main aim is to overthrow British rule in India.

Debidayal's father was loyal to the British and Debi does not like to betray his father. But he realizes gradually, that if he is to prove himself a dedicated freedom fighter. He emerges as the defiant hero of the event when he is arrested and is sent to the Andaman. He refuses to see anyone except his sister, Sundari in the prison before he leaves for the Andaman. "*Gian survives and continues to grow while Debidayal becomes a victim of the Hindu-Muslim riots*"⁵

Malgonkar steadily brings Debidayal into the centre of action of this part of the transformation he undergoes. His morale is high and his devotion to the cause still is very deep. His spirit therefore remains unbroken. His compassion for Mumtaz transforms him and compels him to review the philosophy of his life.

After the plane tragedy, Shafi betrays his Hindu friends and manages to escape. Debidayal is arrested, convicted, and sent to the Andamans. Shafi's betrayal is shocking because so far he had been working hard for Hindu-Muslim Sikh unity. Hafiz, the top Muslim leader succeeds in brainwashing people like Shafi who easily discard their mantle of unity and consider Hindus as their sworn enemies. Youth like Shafi and Debidayal were mainstays of communal harmony. Shafi's betrayal dealt a great blow to Debidayal who is now serving a term in Andaman jail. It is also an indication of the emerging communal consciousness in the country.

Gian is disturbed by various family problems and feuds, unable to stick to his ideals of nonviolence burning to take revenge on Vishnu Dutt for his brother Hari's murder. In a helpless rage, Gian kills Vishnu Dutt. Gian continues his nefarious activities in Duriabad, contacts Tekchand, Kerwad manages to earn the family's goodwill by proclaiming himself Debidayal's friend from Andaman, gets a job with the Kerwad construction company and also develops ties with Sundari, Debi's sister. Things suddenly take a turn for the worse.

Gian is a man of conflict. He is aware of his weakness and struggles to seek fulfillment in life. At the beginning of the novel, Gian is presented as an impulsive and sudden convert to Gandhism and accepts the call for boycotting the British goods. Gian's growth begins with his shedding the principle of non-violence as a way of life. He seems to debate that it was a political expedient in the struggle against the British. It could not serve as a philosophy of life itself. He gets deflated by his collisions with reality. His fall from non-violence is quick and headlong. He kills Vishnu Dutt with the same axe with which Vishnu Dutt killed his brother. Towards the end, he affirms the meaning of his life through an act of unselfish love born of deep understanding.

Manohar Malgonkar has pictured Gian's psychological realism very well through this episode which is the turning point in Gian's life"⁶ Gian appears to be typical of the youth of India, vacillating always seeking new anchors, and new directions and devoid of any basic convictions. Malgonkar takes Gian through all the stages of development and his growth towards his moral maturity. Among the masculine protagonists of Malgonkar, Gian Talwar in the novel *A Bend in the Ganges* becomes very prominent particularly for his long and unmitigated sufferings.

In Duriabad, Gian and Shafi clash and Shafi kills Mrs. Tekchand and Gian kills Shafi. The pandemonium is let loose and nobody knows who is doing what. Ultimately Gian escapes to India but somehow his conscience pricks him. After going through the fire or remorse he changes his attitude, goes back to Duriabad and saves Sundari, and takes her to the safety and security of India.

The last chapter titled "the land they were leaving has a touch of nostalgia about it. But most heart-rending is the callous way in which old Mr. Tekchand is left behind as Sundari and Gian are ordered to move ahead by the traffic-controlling office. We can't hold up the convoy for somebody's old man is the last line of the novel.

"Malgonkar shows that the partition which came as a fellow traveler of freedom was not a consequence of an overnight decision of the leaders."7 A Bend in the Ganges is concerned with the theme of an individual's quest for fulfillment in moral identity. Gian and Debidayal represent two different ideologies of life. Both Gian and Debidayal with their contrasting nature and conflicting ways come to realize the same redeeming factor affirmation through love. In the course of events, Gian survives and continues to grow while Debidayal becomes a victim of the Hindu-Muslim riots.

Conclusion:

Malgonkar is famous because of his use of language. It is simple to understand and his stories provide us a sense of realism. There is a perfect match between the plot and the setting. Readers are enlightened to read such a novel because it seems that it is a proper documentation of the events of partition.

Malgonkar gives the impression that he wants to tell the whole story from the point of view of revolutionaries who condemn non-violence as the philosophy of sheep. He depicts man's inner urge for violence or his hidden capacity for violence. "Here, Malgonkar portrait the horrible scenario of the violence and riot that how the Indian hates each other during the time of partition of India."8 Nonviolence indeed demands greater courage than violence. Malgonkar paints a vivid picture of the decade preceding India's freedom to show man's innate weakness for violence, the instinct for self-preservation during turbulent times.

REFERENCES:

1. Udaya Raj Paudel. "Communication of Violence, Religious Culture and Nationalism in A Bend in the Ganges". American Research Journal of History and Culture ; V4, 11; pp: 1-13
2. Usha Bande (2016) *Makers of Indian Literature Manohar Malgonkar*: Sahitya Akademi
3. Manohar Malgonkar (2022) *A Bend in the Ganges*: HarperCollins Publishers
4. A Padmanabhan 2002 *The Fictional World of Manohar Malgonkar*: Atlantic Publishers and Distributors
5. M. Rajagopalachari (1989) *The Novels of Manohar Malgonkar*: Prestige Books
6. Seema Miglani (2009) *Historical Narrative: A Study of Manohar Malgonkar's Fiction*: Vayu Education of India
7. Dr. Vidushi Sharma, "A BEND IN THE GANGES: A NOVEL OF PARTITION, VIOLENCE AND VENGEANCE: A REINTERPRETATION." Journal of Critical Reviews, ISSN - 2394-5125, VOL 7, ISSUE 14, 2020 pp: 4075-4077
8. Vijay Shiture, Dr. Pramod Kumar -- Locating Narrative of Violence in Manohar a Bend in Malgonkar's The Ganges -- Palarch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology 17(6). ISSN 1567-214x